

Synthesis of Diphenyl Acetates.

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The present investigation describes the synthesis of diphenyl acetates which are intermediates in the synthesis of phenanthrenes according to the method previously described by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 591).

4-Methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylic ester, obtained by the method of Kötze and Michels (*Annalen*, 1906, **348**, 95), is condensed with ethyl chloroacetate when diethyl 4-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (I) is obtained. This on hydrolysis yields 4-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid (II). After esterification it is treated with phenyl magnesium bromide when ethyl 1-hydroxy-4-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate (III, R = Me) is obtained. This on dehydrogenation by means of sulphur yields ethyl 4-methyldiphenyl-2-acetate (IV) (*cf.* Sherwood, Short and Woodcock, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 322).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

By following the same method, 6-methyldiphenyl-2-acetate has been prepared from 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylic ester (Kötz, *Annalen*, 1905, 342, 321).

In the preparation of diethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate by Kötz and Bieber's method (*Annalen*, 1906, 350, 240) for the synthesis of ethyl 5-methyldiphenyl-2-acetate, it is observed that the product of reaction of 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylic ester and ethyl chloroacetate is always contaminated with 2-methylhexane-1:5:6-tricarboxylic ester, formed by the ring fission. The boiling point of the above product recorded by us when the reaction is carried out in benzene in presence of molecular sodium is 163° - $166^{\circ}/5$ mm. Further we notice the following difference between Kötz's and our compound.

Kötz.	The present author.
B.p. 194° - $195^{\circ}/12$ mm.	B.p. 163° - $66^{\circ}/5$ mm.
↓ On hydrolysis with methyl alcoholic potash	↓ On hydrolysis with conc. HCl
5-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid (gummy)	5-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid (crystalline, m.p. $94-95^{\circ}$)
↓ Esterified either through Ag salt or by HCl method	↓ Esterified by HCl method
Very poor yield of ethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate (b. p. not definite due to poor yield), semicarbazone, m.p. 116° .	Good yield of ethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate (b.p. $137^{\circ}/5$ mm) semicarbazone, m.p. $174-75^{\circ}$

Hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetic acid* (V), an intermediate for the synthesis of phenanthrene, has been prepared from ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate (III, R=H). The ester is dehydrated by Darzen's method and the resulting unsaturated ester is reduced catalytically and ethyl hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate, thus obtained, is hydrolysed.

* The work was considerably in progress for the synthesis of phenanthrene from hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetic acid when the result of Cook, Hewell, and Lawrence was published (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 71).

(V)

(VI)

Diethyl 4 (5 or 6)-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate when submitted to Grignard's reaction with phenyl magnesium bromide gives lactones (VI, $R = \text{Me}$, $R' = R'' = \text{H}$; $R' = \text{Me}$, $R = R'' = \text{H}$; $R'' = \text{Me}$; $R = R' = \text{H}$).

Further work in this line is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl 4-Methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate.—Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (20 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (2.5 g.) in alcohol (25 g.) and the solid sodium salt obtained was heated under reflux for 6 hours with ethyl chloroacetate (15 g.). After dilution the product was extracted with ether, and distilled at $165^\circ/5$ mm., yield 14 g.

Substitution of molecular sodium in benzene for sodium ethoxide gave a very good yield. 2.5 G. of molecular sodium in 100 c.c. of benzene were added to 20 g. of ethyl 4-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and left overnight; the solid sodium salt was then heated under reflux for 3–4 hours with ethyl chloroacetate (15 g.). The product was worked up in the usual manner, b. p. $165^\circ/5$ mm., yield 20 g. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 8.1. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m. p. 174° . (Found: N, 12.6. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_5\text{N}_3$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

Diethyl 5-Methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate, obtained from 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and ethyl chloroacetate by the previously described method, distilled at $163^\circ\text{--}66^\circ/5$ mm. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 8.0. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1 per cent).

Diethyl 6-Methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate, obtained from 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylic ester and ethyl chloroacetate

distilled at 158°-162°/8 mm. (Found : C, 62.0; H, 8.0. $C_{14}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1 per cent).

4-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic Acid.—Diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (20 g.) was boiled with 2 vols. of HCl (*d* 1.19) and water (2 : 8) for 8 hours on a sand-bath. After removal of the HCl under reduced pressure, 4-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid distilled at 160-165°/6 mm., yield 10 g. (Found : C, 63.4; H, 8.2. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

5-Methylhexanone-2-acetic Acid was obtained from diethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (20 g.). After removal of the mineral acid under reduced pressure it distilled at 162°/4 mm. and solidified at the room temperature. It crystallised from petroleum ether, m. p. 94-95°; yield 8-10 g. (Found : C, 63.5; H, 8.1. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

6-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic Acid, obtained from diethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate, distilled at 162-166°/6 mm. (Found : C, 63.4; H, 8.0. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.5; H, 8.2 per cent).

Ethyl 4-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate.—4-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid (10 g.) was esterified at room temperature with 3 parts of alcohol, saturated at 0° with dry hydrochloric acid and keeping overnight. After dilution it was extracted with ether and worked up in the usual manner, b. p. 129°, 8 mm., yield 8 g. (Found : C, 66.5; H, 9.0. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.0 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 210-11°. (Found : N, 16.6. $C_{12}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires N, 16.4 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate, obtained by esterifying 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid (10 g.) collected at 127°/5 mm., yield 9 g. (Found : C, 66.4; H, 9.1. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.0 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 174-75°. (Found : N, 16.7. $C_{12}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires N, 16.4 per cent).

Ethyl 6-Methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate, obtained by esterifying 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetic acid, distilled at 125°-130°/8 mm. (Found : C, 66.6; H, 9.0. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.0 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-4-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate.—PhMgBr (from 5.5 c.c. of bromobenzene and 1.3 g. of Mg) was added drop by drop to an ethereal solution of 4-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate (10.5 g.), kept cool by means of ice. The reaction

mixture was left overnight and the product decomposed by means of dilute sulphuric acid. After removing ether it was distilled at $168-178^{\circ}/8$ mm., yield 4 g. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 8.5. $C_{17}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 73.9; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-5-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate was obtained by the action of $PhMgBr$ on 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate (10 g.), b.p. $165-75^{\circ}/7$ mm., yield 3 g. (Found: C, 74.4; H, 8.7. $C_{17}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 73.9; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-6-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate was obtained by the action of $PhMgBr$ on 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-acetate, b.p. $160-70^{\circ}/7$ mm. (Found: C, 74.3; H, 8.8. $C_{17}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 73.9; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 4-Methyldiphenyl-2-acetate.—Ethyl 1-hydroxy-4-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate was heated with sulphur for 4 to 5 hours at $200-240^{\circ}$ and the product after washing with caustic alkali was distilled at $160-67^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: C, 79.9; H, 7.0. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 7.08 per cent).

Ethyl 6-Methyldiphenyl-2-acetate was obtained by heating ethyl 1-hydroxy-5-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate with sulphur as above, b.p. $160-163^{\circ}/9$ mm. (Found: C, 80.0; H, 7.1. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 7.08 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Methyldiphenyl-2-acetate was obtained by heating ethyl 1-hydroxy-5-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate with sulphur as described above, b.p. $160-65^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: C, 80.1; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 7.08 per cent).

Ethyl Hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate.—Thionyl chloride (17 g.) was added slowly to a well-stirred ice-cold mixture of ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate (32 g.), anhydrous ether (70 c.c.), and pyridine (29 c.c.). Stirring and cooling were continued for 2 hours, the solution was then poured into water and the product after washing with dilute caustic alkali was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed, dried, and distilled, b.p. $165-75^{\circ}/7$ mm. (Found: C, 78.1; H, 8.2. $C_{16}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 78.6; H, 8.3 per cent). 5 G. of the substance in alcohol (40 c.c.) were shaken for 8 days with platinum oxide (0.1 g.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen when the theoretical quantity of hydrogen was absorbed. Ethyl hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate boiled at $168-72^{\circ}/8$ mm. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 8.8. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.1; H, 8.8 per cent).

Hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetic Acid was obtained by refluxing ethyl hexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate with alcoholic potash for 2 hours. The

alcohol was distilled off and after dilution the unchanged ester was removed by ether. The aqueous layer was concentrated and after acidification the free acid was extracted with ether, the ether removed, the product kept in a desiccator for 2 days when it solidified. It was finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 168-70°. (Found: C, 76.7, H, 8.3. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$: C, 77.6; H, 8.3 per cent).

Lactone of Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-2-acetic acid-4-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-carboxylate.— $PhMgBr$ (from 5 c.c. bromobenzene and 1.2 g. of Mg.) was added drop by drop to an ethereal solution of diethyl-4-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (13 g.) kept cool by means of ice

A gelatinous precipitate separated and the reaction mixture was left overnight and then decomposed by means of dilute sulphuric acid. After removing the ether it was subjected to fractional distillation in vacuum and the product collecting at 200-220°/7 mm., was found to solidify at room temperature. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 112°, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.2 per cent).

Lactone of Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-5-methyl-2-acetic acid-hexahydrodiphenyl-2-carboxylate was obtained by the action of $PhMgBr$ on diethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (13 g.) by a method similar to that described above, b.p. 210-20°/7 mm., yield 4 g. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 7.1. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.2 per cent).

Lactone of Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-2-acetic acid-6-methylhexahydrodiphenyl-2-carboxylate was obtained by the action of $PhMgBr$ on diethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate, b.p. 205-15°/mm. (Found: C, 71.1; H, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.2 per cent).

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